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A Peer Reviewed (Refereed) International Journal**Article Information**Received: 27th Feb, 2025Accepted: 28th Feb, 2025Published: 25th April, 2025**INNOVATIVENESS OF SENIOR PASTORS AND GROWTH OF CHRIST
APOSTOLIC CHURCH IN NIGERIA****¹Tunde David ASOKEJI, ²Festus M. EPETIMEHIN, & ³Emmanuel Makanjuola
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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the nexus of innovativeness of senior pastors and growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria. The study employed quantitative research design. The population of the study was 4,360 (C.A.C. Information System, 2024). The sample size was determined by using Yamane (1967) formula. The sample size was three hundred and sixty-seven (367). Hence, 367 copies of questionnaire were administered purposively to senior pastors of Christ Apostolic Church who are on the ranks of Districts-Coordinating Council (DCC) Superintendent, Zonal Superintendent, and District Superintendent in the thirty-six (36) states, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja in Nigeria. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was deployed in the analysis of data collected. Descriptive statistical analysis such as frequencies and percentages were used while inferential statistical analysis such as Regression and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were carried out on the data collected. Findings from the study showed significant positive effect of innovativeness on growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria ($B = 0.432$; $T = 4.979$; $p = 0.000$). The study concluded that innovativeness of senior pastors has significant effect on growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Innovativeness, Pastors, Church Growth, Christ Apostolic Church, Nigeria***INTRODUCTION**

Christ Apostolic Church is the first Pentecostal Church in Nigeria (Asodati, 2016). She can be viewed as the crown of a series of spiritual awakenings in Nigeria in 1930 (Asodati, 2016). It began in the Saint Saviour's Anglican Church, Ijebu-Ode as a Prayer and Bible Study group known as the Precious Stone. However, the group left the Anglican Communion because of perceived spiritual lethargy of the Church. Prominent members of the Prayer group included David Osmond Odubanjo, Joseph B. Sadare, Isaac Babalola Akinyele; the first educated Olubadan of Ibadan, and Sophia Ajayi nee Odunlami; a woman with Prophetic anointing through whom great miracles were wrought by the Lord (Asodati, 2016).

On October 9, 1928, Joseph Ayo Babalola was called by God, while working on the Ilesha-Akure Road, specifically at Ikeji-Arakeji, with a mandate to start a prophetic ministry (Alokan, 2009). Later, he connected with the praying group in Lagos where he was baptized at Ebute Elefun and eventually became the arrow-head of the 1930 revival which broke out at Oke-Ooye Ilesa in present-day Osun State, Nigeria. The praying group entered into some alliances which did not work out well. According to Olowe (2018), the name "Apostolic Church" was reportedly revealed to Apostle Babalola even before the British Apostolic Church (or British Brothers from Bradford, England) came in 1931. The Church evolved severally as Nigeria Apostolic Church (NAC), United Apostolic Church (UAC), The Apostolic Church (TAC) before the name Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) was adopted eventually.

Christ Apostolic Church was incorporated with the Corporate Affairs Commission in the year 1941 as number 147 under the Perpetual Land Acts of Nigeria. With an estimated membership of about 2 million and a pastoral population of about 12 thousand, the Christ Apostolic Church can well be called a Mega Church. However, it has been observed that the vast Human Resources of the church are yet to be fully optimized to engender her further growth.

Christ Apostolic Church is one of the frontline African Indigenous churches in Nigeria. The church branches are all over the nooks and crannies of Nigeria. Indigenization and inculturation of Christ Apostolic Church has gained her some measure of respect. The factors responsible for the advent and growth of Christ Apostolic Church are hinged on the features of African Independent churches and methods adopted for church planting. The features of CAC that aided growth include liturgy, prayer, faith healing, zeal for evangelism and revival.

Growth is a process of change or development physically, mentally, emotionally, profitably i.e. increases in size, economy activity while the Church is defined as a Christian body, a set of people that are called out from the worldliness to proclaim the love and glory of God (Hornby, 2006). Therefore, Church Growth is the physical and spiritual expansion, development and increase of the Church which is the body of Christ. The key attributes of church growth are passion for the "Great Commission" and willingness to apply research to attracting members, including quantitative method (Newton, 2007; Owoeye, 2011). Willingness which is otherwise known as "risk propensity" is one of the attributes of entrepreneurial mindset.

Several studies from developed countries have shown that church attendance in the years to come will dwindle, and the causes were attributed among others, to senior pastors not exercising strong leadership skills, the aging of the membership, inadequate church planting strategies (Malphurs, 2009; Olson, 2008; Bartlow, 2015). Furthermore, Church planting and starting new ministry initiatives requires having some form of entrepreneurial attitude (Bartlow, 2015). Based on the foregoing, this study aims to determine the nexus of innovativeness of senior pastors and growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria.

II. Literature Review

Creativity and innovation are essential components of entrepreneurial mindset. Assessing these parameters involves measuring an individual's ability to generate novel ideas, think outside the box, and develop innovative solutions to problems. Creativity and innovation can be evaluated through various methods, such as creative thinking tasks, ideation exercises, or assessments of past creative achievements. The entrepreneurial mindset encourages creative thinking and innovation. Aspiring entrepreneurs can cultivate their creativity by adopting techniques like brainstorming, mind mapping, and lateral thinking. They can also embrace an experimental mindset that encourages trying new approaches, embracing feedback, and iterating on their ideas.

This study is focusing on psychological traits theory that was propounded by Rauch & Frese (2007). The theory focuses on the individual characteristics and personality traits that are associated with entrepreneurial success. It suggests that traits such as risk-taking propensity, need for achievement, locus of control, and tolerance for ambiguity play a significant role in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset. This theory is applicable to this study based on its attributes as it relates to entrepreneurial mindsets of pastors and growth of Christ Apostolic Church. Hence, Church Growth principle is a universal truth which, when properly interpreted and applied, contributes significantly to the growth of churches and denominations. It is a truth of God which leads His church to spread His Good News, plant church after church, and increase his Body (McGavran, 2013).” There are three types of church growth such as biological growth, transfer growth, conversion growth (Acts 2:41ff.), Several related studies have been carried out on the nexus of entrepreneurial mindset and performance of an organization.

Colombelli, Loccisano, Panelli, Pennisi, and Serraino (2022) investigated the impacts of Challenge-Based Learning programs on entrepreneurial skills, and on the mindset and intentions of university students, through a quantitative approach. The analyzed period for this study was between January 2019 to January 2021, a period that included 11 challenges which involved approximately 300 students. The sample was composed of 127 students who filled in a questionnaire administered before and after participation in the challenge-based program so as to identify any possible changes in the Ex-Ante vs. Ex-Post events. The results revealed that the program positively and significantly affected the entrepreneurial mindset and skills, such as creativity, financial literacy and planning, of the students who took part. The empirical evidence also shows an increase in the students’ entrepreneurial intention, although the effect is not statistically significant for this first set of data. This study is limited to quantitative research method, further studies may consider mixed method.

Adewumi (2021) examined the students’ entrepreneurial mindset in the era of Global Health Pandemic in Lagos state, Nigeria. Exploratory research design was deployed in this study using qualitative research technique such as semi-structured interview. A total number of twenty-four (24) final year students were considered in this study. This study deployed two types of non-probability such as snowball and purposive strategies across two faculties. First, all the final year students across the considered departments were recruited through snowballing to ensure that only final year undergraduate students were recruited for this study. This sampling strategy was achieved through initial referrals from at least a student from each Department. Further referrals were made in identifying other students who meet up with the sample definition. Hence, the final year students with entrepreneurship experience were interviewed through telephone. The interview lasted between May and August, 2020 culminating in a total of four months. The transcripts interviews were all transcribed into text and subjected to the NVivo (v. 12) qualitative software for the identification of themes that support the research problem. Findings from the study shows that the development of students’ entrepreneurship mind-set to include attitude development, preparedness, being business savvy and a stimulating business environment. Others include effective mobilization of human and material resources and appropriate students’ cognitive cognizance. The persistent economic downturn was argued as the link between the global health pandemic and the dwindling rate of graduate jobs, whereas appropriate entrepreneurship education, content and curriculum was advanced as important indicators for a sustaining students’ entrepreneurial mind-set. Meanwhile, this study is limited to final year undergraduate students, further studies may consider entrepreneurial mindsets of pastors using mixed method. In addition to that, the study did not indicate the actual population of this study, hence, the sample size used might not be scientific. Further studies may consider scientific sample size.

Gubik and Bartha (2021) examined the perception of students and the efficacy of universities in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset. The study used 2018 GUESSS (Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students' Survey) database, which includes 9,667 answers for Hungary, to develop a general linear model. The model suggests that students' entrepreneurial intentions, attitudes toward entrepreneurship, self-efficacy, social norms, as well as the university, and the field of study all have a small but statistically significant impact on how students perceive the entrepreneurial ecosystem within the university. The study concludes that more emphasis on shaping attitudes and arousing student interest could increase the efficiency of entrepreneurship education. Nevertheless, the study is limited to entrepreneurial mindsets of universities students, further studies may consider entrepreneurial mindsets of pastors. Furthermore, the study is limited to quantitative research techniques, further studies may consider mixed methods research. Also, the study is limited to entrepreneurial mindsets of universities students, further studies may consider entrepreneurial mindsets of high school students.

Handayati, Wulandari, Soetjipto, Wibowo, and Narmaditya (2020) explored how entrepreneurship education determines students' entrepreneurial intentions as well as examine the emerging role of the entrepreneurial mindset in supporting this relationship. A quantitative method was applied to gain a better understanding of the relationship between the variables. The participants of this study were recruited from several vocational students in East Java of Indonesia by using an online survey. The survey was conducted from January to March 2020, using online forms. A total of 470 questionnaires were received, and after the validating action, approximately 450 questionnaires were verified applicable. The data were calculated utilizing Partial Least Square (PLS) approach to Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The calculation and judgment of a Partial Least Square (PLS) model in this study was provided in two stages: First, the assessment of validity and reliability of the construct to determine the goodness of measures. Second, the evaluation of structural model to evaluate the hypotheses under research. The findings from this study indicate that entrepreneurship education positively influences both students' entrepreneurial intentions and an entrepreneurial mindset. It also reveals a robust correlation between entrepreneurship mindset and students' entrepreneurship intentions. Lastly, this study's finding shows that the entrepreneurship mindset has successfully mediated the relationship between entrepreneurial education and students' entrepreneurial intention. Nevertheless, this study is limited to quantitative research technique, further studies may integrate both quantitative and qualitative research technique for robust report. In addition to that, further studies may be done in Nigeria by replicating the variables used the study.

Wardana, Narmaditya and Wibowo (2020) investigate the relationship between students' entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial mindset as well as understanding the mediating role of attitude and self-efficacy. The study adopted a convenience random sampling method for data collection. Respondents were from several universities in Malang of East Java in Indonesia undergoing an online survey and were calculated using structural equation modeling (SEM). Three hundred and ninety (390) students participated in the study. It also involved students in the first-year and second-year study by approximately 2.6 percent and 2.4 percent, respectively. The respondents came from the various subject studies, including economics, social sciences and humanities, sciences and engineering. Findings from the study show that entrepreneurship education successfully influences entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial attitude, and the entrepreneurial mindset. On the other hand, entrepreneurial self-efficacy promotes entrepreneurial attitude instead of the entrepreneurial mindset. Furthermore, entrepreneurial attitude plays an essential role in mediating both entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy toward students' entrepreneurial mindset. The study recommends that first, the university needs to change the curriculum of entrepreneurship courses by bringing practitioners as instructors, conducting fieldwork with more compositions than theories in the classroom. Second, the university provides assistance to students in making new products by facilitating several

supporting activities, including business capital, in financial matters. Furthermore, the need for attitudes towards entrepreneurship students in their business is expected to create a more profitable business financial condition by making efficiency in several production aspects while still producing the best quality products. Lastly, the university makes support to students in forming an entrepreneurial mindset. This study is limited to students' entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial mindset using quantitative research techniques, further studies may consider implication of entrepreneurial mindset of pastors on church growth using mixed method research technique for robust results.

Barba-Sánchez and Atienza-Sahuquillo (2017) examined the impact of entrepreneurial motivations on entrepreneurial intentions among future engineers (Industrial Engineering and Computer Engineering) at the University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain. The participants in this study were four hundred and twenty-three (423) final year engineering students which comprises two hundred and nineteen (219) industrial engineering students and two hundred and four (204) computer engineering students. Among the students who participated, 64.7% followed an optional course in the fields of business management and entrepreneurial skills as part of their professional development, and 35.3% had not received any entrepreneurship education at all, prior to the study. The study proposed a mix of action-oriented teaching that encourages project-based learning. The methods most often employed for entrepreneurial motivations are readings, class discussion, business plans, using cases of prestigious entrepreneurs, and inviting local entrepreneurs to give lectures. The method of data collection was online student questionnaire that was administered on the engineering students. The students completed the online questionnaire, both at the beginning of the study to identify the starting situation in terms of their entrepreneurial motivation and intention, and also at the end of the academic year in order to analyze and assess the incidence of this experience on entrepreneurial orientation and motivation. The implication is that the entrepreneurial intention was studied in two time periods as the students were asked about their future career choices before the entrepreneurial training begins (ex-ant: before training) and after the training was completed (ex-post: after the training).

Findings from the study show that computer engineers consider it more important to “develop professionally and personally” rather than “cover their personal needs”. In a similar way to what happened in job prospects, in motivation there is a higher level of agreement in terms of average values among industrial engineering students. Findings from the study further shows that the entrepreneurial profile of engineering students confirm the positive effect that entrepreneurship education has on their intention to create a business, while at the same time helping the various public authorities to establish measures and strategies to maximize resource employment in the eagerness to promote entrepreneurship.

The study, however, concluded that both industrial engineers and computer engineers have a high need for achievement and independence. The implication is that the option of creating a business is seen to gain independence and not rely financially on the family economy in view of the difficulty of finding a job in the current situation. The study further concluded that despite having a slightly less favorable motivational configuration, computer engineering students have greater entrepreneurial intentions than industrial engineering students. This may be explained by the moderator effects that entrepreneurial training on this relation. The study also concluded that entrepreneurship education has significant positive effect on entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students in the study area. Meaning that, that there is an improvement in entrepreneurial intentions among engineering students and that of computer engineering students. Despite the importance of this study, there are some gaps identified in the study. Firstly, the use of closed, structured questionnaire makes it impossible to explore in greater depth the nature of causal relations; something which is emphasized in cross-sectional studies. In addition, the sample only consists of engineering students from one university in Spain, so that the conclusions

obtained cannot be generalized to other groups of students, particularly those who have opted for a degree in Business Administration and Management. Future research should use new and more diverse samples. There is need for further primary studies to contribute to these research areas so that more accurate conclusions could be drawn. Furthermore, the methodology used, i.e., linear regression analysis, could be supplemented with other more suitable methodologies such as stepwise regression to highlight moderator effects. In this regard, future research can further explore moderator effects (both of students' professional expectations and their context perception) on the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and business creation intent among different groups of students and possibly widening the diversity of the analyzed groups.

III. Methodology

The study employed quantitative research design. The population of the study was 4,360 (C.A.C. Information System, 2024). The sample size was determined by using Yamane (1967) formula. The sample size was three hundred and sixty-seven (367). Hence, 367 copies of questionnaire were administered purposively to senior pastors of Christ Apostolic Church who are in the cadres of District Coordinating Council (DCC), Zonal Superintendent, and District Superintendent in the thirty-six (36) states, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja in Nigeria. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was deployed in the analysis of data collected. Descriptive statistical analysis such as frequencies and percentages were used while inferential statistical analysis such as Regression and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were carried out on the data collected.

IV Results and Discussion

Findings from the study showed the socio-demographic attributes of the respondents. The Table 1 shows that majority (82.4%) of the respondents are District Superintendents, followed by Zonal superintendents (10.7%) while the remaining 6.9% respondents are District Coordinating Council (DCC). This shows that district Superintendent has rank with highest percentage of the respondents while District Coordinating Council has least percentage of the respondents.

The Table 1 further shows the present region of the respondents with the majorities (26.9%, 18.9%, 14.3% and 10.2%) coming from Akiling Region (Headquarters: Agege, Lagos), Babajide Region (Headquarters: Odo Owa), Orogun Region (Headquarters: Osogbo) and Medaiyese Region (Headquarters: Abuja) respectively. The other respondents are from Odubanjo Region (Headquarters: Akure) (8.2%), Akinyele Region (Headquarters: Ebute-Elefun, Lagos) (4.6%), Hanson Region (Headquarters: Benin City, Edo) (4.6%), Essien Region (Headquarters: Abeokuta) (3.1%), Sophia Ajayi Region- (Headquarters: Ado Ekiti) (2.6%), Pearce Region- (Headquarters: Mushin, Lagos) (2%), Adelaja Region (Headquarters: Kano) (1.5%), Babalola Region (Headquarters: Ibadan) (1.5%), Olutimehin Region (Headquarters: Port-Harcourt) (1%), Orekoya Region (Headquarters: Jos) (0.5%), and Odusona Region (Headquarters: Enugu) (0.5%). The implication is that Akilin Region has highest percentage of respondents while Orekoya Region has least percentage of respondents.

Table 1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Present Rank	Frequenc y	Percent
District Coordinating Council (DCC)	27	6.9
Zonal Superintendent	42	10.7

District Superintendent	322	82.4
Total	391	100.0
Present Region		
Adelaja Region (Headquarters: Kano)	6	1.5
Akiling Region (Headquarters: Agege, Lagos)	105	26.9
Akinyele Region (Headquarters: Ebute-Elefun, Lagos)	18	4.6
Babajide Region (Headquarters: Odo Owa)	72	18.4
Babalola Region (Headquarters: Ibadan)	6	1.5
Essien Region (Headquarters: Abeokuta)	12	3.1
Hanson Region (Headquarters: Benin City, Edo)	18	4.6
Medaiyese Region (Headquarters: Abuja)	40	10.2
Odubanjo Region (Headquarters: Akure)	32	8.2
Orogun Region (Headquarters: Osogbo)	56	14.3
Odusona Region (Headquarters: Enugu)	2	.5
Olutimehin Region (Headquarters: Port-Harcourt)	4	1.0
Orekoya Region (Headquarters: Jos)	2	.5
Pearce Region- (Headquarters: Mushin, Lagos)	8	2.0
Sophia Ajayi Region- (Headquarters: Ado Ekiti)	10	2.6
Total	391	100.0

Table 2 shows the years of ordination of the respondents, the table shows that 50.9% of the respondents were ordained between 1991-2000. This implies that the church has a highly experienced pastoral staff, followed by 41.2% of the respondents were ordained between 2001-2010 while the remaining respondents, 6.9% and 1% of the respondents were ordained between 1980-1990 and 2011-2020 respectively. The implication is that the respondents are highly experienced in the pastoral field. Concerning the level of education of the respondents, majorities (30.4% and 36.8%) of the responds are with B.Sc. /HND and M.Sc./MBA degrees respectively. This implies that the church has highly educated pastoral staff while the remaining respondents (20.7% and 12%) had Ph.D. and less than degree respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents are elites.

The Table 2 shows the year of last promotion of the respondents, the table shows that majority (54.7%) of the respondent were last promoted in 2021 till date. This shows that pastoral staff in the church are highly motivated, followed by 33.2% that were last promoted between 2011-2020. The Table 2 further shows that 10.2% and 1.8% of the remaining respondents were last promoted

in the year 2001-2010 and 1991-2000 respectively. The implication is that they are highly motivated because their promotions are neither denied nor delayed by the church administrators. All of those attributes; wealth of experience, highly educated, and motivation are sacrosanct to productive outcomes, otherwise called, church growth.

Table 2 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Year of Ordination		
1980-1990	27	6.9
1991-2000	199	50.9
2001-2010	161	41.2
2011-2020	4	1.0
Total	391	100.0
Highest Level of Education		
Less than Degree	47	12.0
B. Sc./HND	119	30.4
M.Sc./MBA	144	36.8
Ph.D.	81	20.7
Total	391	100.0
Year of Last Promotion		
1991-2000	7	1.8
2001-2010	40	10.2
2011-2020	130	33.2
2021 till date	214	54.7
Total	391	100.0

The table further shows the number of branches met upon resumption at the current station, it was revealed in the table that majority (42.2%) of the respondents met only one branch upon resumption at the current station, follow by two branches (25.6%), three branches (21.5%), four branches (9%), five branches and above (1.3%) and nothing (0.5%), were met upon resumption at the current station.

The Table 3 further shows the number of additional branches that were planted since resumption of respondents at the current station. It was revealed in the Table 3 that majority (45.5%) of the respondents indicated that they have planted at least five additional branches since they resumed at their current station. This implies a branch growth rate of about 500%. Followed by additional; four branches (15.9%), one branch (13.8%), three branches (13.3%), and three branches (13.3%). This finding implies church growth from the view of the number of branches met on resumption and the additional branches planted.

Table 3 Number of branches before resumption and Present branches

Number of Branches Met Upon Resumption		
Nothing	2	.5
One Branch	165	42.2
Two Branches	100	25.6
Three Branches	84	21.5
Four Branches	35	9.0
Five Branches and above	5	1.3
Total	391	100.0
Additional Branches Planted Since Resumption		
One branch	54	13.8
two branches	45	11.5
three branches	52	13.3
Four branches	62	15.9
Five branches and above	178	45.5
Total	391	100.0

Table 4 shows the nexus between innovativeness and church growth in the study area. The Table 4 shows that majority (40.4% and 54.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively with the idea that they believe change is essential for growth and also open to learning new methods. While only 3.3%, 0.8% and 1.3% of the remaining respondents were indifference,

disagreed and strongly disagreed with the idea that they believe change is essential for growth and open to learning new methods respectively.

Table 4 further shows that most of the respondents (89.3% and 6.6%) strongly agreed and disagreed with the idea respectively that they try new approaches in church administration to improve the worship experience of the congregants while only 2%, 0.8% and 1.3% of the remaining respondents were indifference, disagreed and strongly disagreed with the notion.

Still on Table 4, it was revealed that majority (73.7% and 21.5%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively with the idea that they adopt new methods in ministry without compromising Christian values. Though, only 2.8%, 0.8% and 1.3% of the remaining respondents were indifference, disagreed and strongly disagreed with the idea that they adopt new methods in ministry without compromising Christian values. This shows that more than half of the respondents are quite innovative. In fact, more than half of them are open to learning new methods of growing their church assemblies and are also willing to try new approaches in church administration to improve members' worship experience. However, such approaches must not violate or compromise established Biblical Christian values.

Table 4 Innovativeness and Church Growth

Innovativeness (IN) [I believe change is essential for growth and am open to learning new methods]	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	5	1.3
Disagree	3	.8
Indifference	13	3.3
Agree	212	54.2
Strongly Agree	158	40.4
Total	391	100.0
Innovativeness (IN) [I try new approaches in church administration to improve the worship experience]		
Strongly Disagree	5	1.3
Disagree	3	.8
Indifference	8	2.0
Agree	26	6.6
Strongly Agree	349	89.3
Total	391	100.0
Innovativeness (IN) [I adopt new methods in ministry without compromising Christian values]		
Strongly Disagree	5	1.3
Disagree	3	.8
Indifference	11	2.8
Agree	84	21.5
Strongly Agree	288	73.7
Total	391	100.0

Test of Hypothesis

H₀₁: innovativeness does not have significant effect on growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria

Table 5 shows a significant positive effect of innovativeness on growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria ($B = 0.432$; $T = 4.979$; $p = 0.000$). The implication is that a unit increase in innovativeness will cause significant increase in the growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria by 43%. Based on the information in Table 5 however, the hypothesis two is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that innovativeness does has significant effect on the growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.685	0.101		56.232	0.000
	innovativeness	0.432	0.087	0.424	4.979	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Growth of Christ Apostolic Church

V. Conclusion

The study concluded that innovativeness of senior pastors has significant effect on growth of Christ Apostolic Church in Nigeria.

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